

Figure S1. Bacteriological isolation showing colonies compatible with *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* (MAP, circle) at 28 weeks post infection in HEYMP medium from the vermiform appendix rabbit ID3 (14 weeks of incubation).

Figure S2. Amplification of *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* (MAP) DNA by PCR IS900. MW lane; Molecular weight marker (MW, Invitrogen, USA) 100 bp; lanes 1-2 amplifications products 314 bp (arrow) obtained from blood rabbit ID1 and ID2; lane 3 rabbit ID3 negative result, lane 4 negative control (water) and lane 5 positive control (MAP colony DNA).